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A Novel W/TiN/Ta Compound Shaped Charge Liner

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Introduction

The shaped charge liners are widely applied in the modern ammunition and certain industries, e.g. oil, mining, geology, etc. [1]. In many applications it is desirable for the jet to penetrate the target material to a depth as great as possible [2].

$$H = (v_j - v_s) \cdot t_p \cdot \sqrt{\rho_j / \rho_s}$$

in which the H is the maximum penetrate depth, the v_j and v_s is the metal jet head and bottom velocity, the t_p is the time before jet broken, the ρ_j and ρ_s is the density of shaped charge liner and target.

[1] Walters W. Introduction to shaped charges. Army Research Laboratory; 2007.

[2] Salih Saran, et al. Experimental Investigations on Aluminum Shaped Charge Liners. Procedia Engineering 58 (2013) 479–486.

Introduction

Traditional copper shaped charge liner

Cheap;

Easy to processing;

Low density and melt point;

Tungsten shaped charge liner

High density and melt point;

High dynamic fracture elongation rate;

High brittleness;

W/TiN/Ta compound

Processing of W/TiN/Ta compound material

LABOX-1575 Spark Plasma Sintering System

The cross section of W/TiN/Ta laminated compound.

Element analysis of W/TiN/Ta Cross Section.

W/TiN/Ta composites with good bonding can be prepared by SPS

The influence of Ta/W thickness ratio

Stress-strain curves of Ta/W composites with different thickness ratios

Fracture surfaces morphologies various Ta/W composites

Cracks distribution of composites with various thickness ratios

Mechanical properties of W/TiN/Ta laminates

Stress-strain curves of three point bending of various W/Ta laminates

Tensile stress-strain curve of various W/Ta laminates

Explosion overload test

The W/TiN/Ta laminates liner and (b) shaped charge liner (c) equipment of explosion overload test

Explosion overload test

The result of explosion overload test

Metal jet formed a penetration hole on the steel target with a hole size of 10.3 mm×6.5 mm and a depth of 28.5 mm.

Explosion overload test

The SEM image of the inner wall of penetrating hole and components distribution of Ta, W and Fe

The XRD diffraction pattern of the inner wall of the penetrating hole

Conclusion

1. The W-Ta composites fabricated by SPS have good mechanical properties.
2. As the interface of W-Ta, TiN coating greatly improves the mechanical properties of W-Ta composites. Tensile strength of W/TiN-Ta reached 754 MPa and three-point bending strength reached 1400MPa.
3. The W/TiN-Ta compound shaped charge liner can form a good metal jet and penetrate the steal target.

Thanks!

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